

PARALINGUISTICS AND SEMIOTICS AS NON-LINGUISTIC MEANS IN VOICE COMMUNICATIONS

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Annotation: Paralinguistics the problem of using non-linguistic means in voice communications Paralinguistics comes from the Greek "para" with the meaning "about" and "Linguistics" -Linguistics. Paralinguistics is a section of linguistics that studies non-verbal (non-linguistic) means, included voice message and betrayals, together with verbal means of semantic information. In addition Paralinguistics, like section of linguistics, means the aggregate of non-verbal means participating in the speech communications. In modern linguistics, there are three types of paralinguistic means: phonation, kinetic and graphic. To background types of paradigmatic means the timbre of speech, its tempo, loudness, the types of the pause melodic phenomena, as well as features of pronunciation of speech sounds, dialectal social and idiolect

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Kinetic components include gestures, selectable poses, silence. Idiolect (from the Greek idios - its own, peculiar, special and (dialect) - a set formal and stylistic features peculiar to speech and a separate medium of the given language. The term "idiolect" is created by the model of the term "dialect" for designation individual variation of language as opposed to territorial and social variations in which particular verbal features are inherent in whole groups or collective of speakers. Idiolect in the narrow sense - only specific speech features of this native speaker: in this aspect, the study of an idiolect is actual before all in poetics, where the focus is on the relationship between general and individual. Characteristics of speech (style), as well as in neurolinguistics where it is necessary to present correlation of individual and typical clinical pictures in different types speech disorders. Neurolinguistics is a scientific discipline that arose at the junction of neurology and linguistics and studying the system of language in relation to the cerebral substratum of linguistic behavior. Episodic observations of disorders of language behavior in focal brain damage known from the Middle Ages, but their systematic study began in the second half of the 19th century. In domestic linguistics, interest in the facts of linguistic Pathology manifestation of Baudouin de Courtenay, V.A. Theotokos,

L.V.Shcherba and others. The graphic types of paralinguistic means are the type of execution of letters and punctuation languages (handwriting), ways of graphic additions to letters, their substitutes (symbols of type and, etc.) Substrate (from Latin Sub-under and stratum-layer, piast) - a set of features of language system. Undeveloped from the internal laws of the development of a given language, the substrate involves ethnic displacement and linguistic assimilation by aliens of the indigenous population through the stage of bilingualism. Within paralinguistics, there are universal, ethno linguistic and idiolectic. Ethno linguistics (from the Greek ethnos - people, tribe and linguistics) -direction in linguistics, studying language in its relation to culture, interaction linguistic, ethno-cultural and ethnopsychological factors in the functioning and the evolution of language. Representatives of this direction in Russia were F.I. Tusnayevev, A.K. Afanasev, A.A. Potebnya and others. As an independent trend of ethnolinguistics originated in the depths of ethnography at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, having been widely developed in the linguistics of the United States since the 1970s. 19th century in connection with the intensive study of numerous Native American tribes of the north, and then Central America. From the first quarter of the 20th century, F. Bois and the first generation of his disciples laid new traditions in American linguistics. Thus, during this period descriptive linguistics arises that excludes semantics from the circles linguistic disciplines. Paralysis tools not only complement the meaning of the verbal message, but

also are the source of information about the speaker (writing) about his social and age traits of the field, the nature of the character and others. Therefore, paralinguistic means are represented to a different degree in each speech unit. In relation to the verbal side of the utterance, paralinguistic means can perform three functions: 1) make additional information (sometimes contradicting the meaning of the verbal): for example, a positive verbal text may accompanied by background characteristics with a negative ratio and etc.); 2) to replace the missed verbal component “do you want to go with us?” To deny, gesture; 3) combined with verbal means, conveying the same meaning “I want to this red ball” to indicate the gesture. Paralinguistic means are not autonomous and closed semiotic system, but can be as elements of ordered semiotic nonverbal systems (Kinesika), as well as individual indicators that are not regulated in the system. Be sure to be present in the speech message, paralinguistic means however, the unpredictability of a real incarnation is different. For example, with uttering a certain type of questions requires a given melody, but the type timbral coloring remains unknown, therefore the type of

melody is a linguistic fact, and the type of timbre is paralinguistic. Some types of paralinguistic means were studied back in the 1930s.

At the present stage of development of human society and its language such the interaction of linguistic and paralinguistic means formed a pragmatic character of language on a universal and national scale. The general human features in this pragmatics will be treated as some universal to specific systems. For example, gestures as such are general qualities, characteristic for the functioning of the sound language, but a special system of gestures will be refer to this national character paralinguistic means, because it is in every language, each nation acquires its own special meaning. The study of the national characteristics of paralinguistic forms, participating in the linguistic communication is therefore as much a necessity as learning the language itself. When interpreting paralinguistic as a sphere of non-verbal behavior some authors consider some ways of human communication as exclusive, semiotic systems that exist independently, independently of the participation of language in the functioning of these systems.¹ Paralinguistic means as an auxiliary functional system and independent secondary sign system. The definition usually emphasizes the sign of the presence and absence of verbal language. This is clearly expressed in the following statement: “Since the exchange of information is possible only with the help of sign systems, or - in the general theory of semiotics - languages, in all cases we are confronted with languages, but languages of a special kind. All of them unites disconnection, lack of words, therefore they are usually called non-verbal” regardless of the origin of such systems, the functioning of all such means of verbal language can be carried out indirectly and only on the basis of existence and possibility of explicit expression of the values of any gestures material of natural language.² In this case, all sign systems, including systems paralinguistic character (gestures, facial expressions), and any kinds of technical systems character (signs of traffic, various symbols), are sign systems secondary character, the significative purpose of which is predetermined in advance the conventional nature of their use. In other words, every phenomenon artificial sign system gets meaning only on the basis of language decoding and is a symbolic representative of some idea expressed in one form or another verbal language (fixed in the instruction, in the concept, in the oral agreement). This understanding of the communicative nature of artificial sign systems leads to

¹ Т.М. Николаева, Б.А. Успенский. Языкознание и паралингвистика, в кн.

«Лингвистические исследования по общей и славянской типологии» М., 1966.р21.

² Верещагин. Е.Вопросы теории – речи и методика преподавания иностранных языков. М.,1969.стр.66.

conclusion that they are an extreme case in the general set of all Paralinguistic means. This part of the seemingly paralinguistic means goes beyond marginal phenomena and forms a completely independent system of sounds, which is subordinated to the general regularities of conventional semantic systems. First of all, it is about pure conditional gestures of a national character that do not interact with any speech signal and, like any sound system, functioning as a normal code, for example, a gesture of solidarity - raising your hand with a fist clenched in your hand or gesture of threat - movement with the index finger, or in sports a whole system of conditional gestures, for example, when marking the “time out”, breaking the rules, removing the player from the field, gestures of approval (applause). Such gestures are perceived as predetermined, or by a verbal act, and function as any codes, for example, rules signals traffic. All these gestures (including here and all kinds of ritual signs), naturally, should be excluded from the notion of “paralinguistic factor”, and their study should be built out of the connection with the language structure, but only on the basis of their description thirty values, regardless of whether this value is fixed in the customs of this or that human collective and is fixed in written documents, agreements, protocols etc. Or this value exists by right of custom. If we consider paralinguistic means in accordance with their internal regularities, it is possible to reveal their semiotic character, since the functioning of these facilities is generally subject to the rules for the use of signals and various kinds of signs. In this case, each such semiotic system will have national features as characteristic features in a series of semiotic non-linguistic human resources. Here you can indicate the different uses of the same gestures, for example, man to express consent, surprise, anger, etc.³ The paralanguage has a certain semiotic meaning, as evidenced by research results in this direction, but at the same time typical, which is especially clearly revealed in the analysis dialogues in art works, where the author's explanations are based on certain paralinguistic phenomena. These include author's remarks: “ironing on the head, blocking the road, snaps his fingers, waving his arms, spreading his hands, shrugs his shoulders, nods, sways, twitches”.⁴

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